

FATHERS' PARENTING INVOLVEMENT AND ADOLESCENT SELF-CONCEPT AT SMPN 4 PARIAMAN

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Abstract

Introduction: The transition period of life that occurs during adolescence determines the self-concept that is formed. One of the factors that influences the formation of this self-concept is the involvement of father's caregiving. **Method:** This type of research is quantitative with a cross-sectional approach. The independent variable is father's caregiving involvement, while the dependent variable is self-concept. The sample taken was 53 students of SMPN 4 Pariaman with a random sampling technique. The research instrument used a questionnaire. Data analysis was carried out univariately to determine the frequency distribution and percentage of father's caregiving involvement and self-concept. The bivariate test used the Chi-Square statistical test at a significance level of 5%. **Result:** Univariate analysis showed that the majority of respondents, namely 29 students (54.7%) had fathers who were less involved in parenting and had a negative self-concept, namely 32 participants (60.38%). Conversely, adolescents with strong father involvement in childcare were more likely to develop a positive self-concept, as evidenced by 20 participants (90.9%). In contrast, those with limited father involvement predominantly formed a negative self-concept, with 27 participants (87.10%). Statistical analysis using the Chi-Square test at an alpha level of 0.05 revealed a p-value = 0.03 and an odds ratio (OR) = 8.50. This study indicates a significant relationship between father involvement in parenting and the development of self-concept among adolescents at SMPN 4 Pariaman. Furthermore, the odds ratio of 8.50 suggests that adolescents with actively involved fathers are 8.50 times more likely to develop a positive self-concept compared to those with less involved fathers. **Discussion:** These findings imply that a father's involvement in parenting significantly influences self-concept formation in adolescents. This aligns with previous studies indicating that children with positive self-concepts tend to have fathers who are actively engaged in parenting, while those with negative self-concepts are more likely to come from families where fathers are minimally involved or not involved at all in parenting. Father's parenting involvement is related to the formation of self-concept in adolescents at SMPN 4 Pariaman, West Sumatra Province.

Keywords: Fathers' parenting, Self-concept, Adolescent

1. INTRODUCTION

Adolescence is a transitional period from childhood to adulthood, characterized by physical changes, biological developments, and mental, emotional, and psychosocial growth. During this time, individuals begin the process of discovering their identity. This stage involves exploring and understanding one's true self, including values, interests, life goals, beliefs, and social roles within society. The development of character during this identity exploration is influenced by the self-concept that is currently being formed. Self-concept refers to a person's perception or evaluation of themselves

across physical, psychological, social, and spiritual dimensions [1]. It encompasses self-awareness, self-assessment, and perceptions of how others view them. A strong sense of self-awareness contributes to a positive self-concept. The process of developing a self-concept is crucial for establishing a robust and stable personal identity.

During adolescence, the development of self-concept can be one of the most challenging aspects of an adolescent's life. Increasing curiosity allows adolescence to expand their social circles. A supportive social environment fosters positivity among an adolescent's, contributing to the formation of a healthy self-concept [2]. Conversely, a negative social environment can adversely affect the development of a negative self-concept. A positive self-concept emerges when a teenager can understand and accept various aspects of themselves in a positive and dynamic manner. In contrast, a negative self-concept develops when a teenager perceives themselves in an irregular way or holds unrealistic ideals about who they should be. A negative self-concept can lead to several consequences, including increased withdrawal, social isolation, shyness, and even serious social disorders [3].

The National Institute of Mental Health in 2023 reported that a significant number of an adolescent's in Indonesia possess a negative self-assessment. Research indicates that a negative self-concept contributes to the rising rates of juvenile delinquency in the country [4]. According to the Central Statistics Agency in 2024, there are approximately 44.25 million teenagers aged 10 to 19 years in Indonesia, accounting for about 25.09% of the population. Around 50% of these teenagers have been documented as engaging in violent behavior towards one another [5]. The Indonesian Child Protection Commission (KPAI) also noted an increase in juvenile delinquency, rising from 16.5% to 17.5%. Furthermore, the National Narcotics Agency (BNN) reported a rise in drug abuse among teenagers, with the number of affected individuals increasing from 2.29 million in 2020 to 3.21 million in 2022 [6]. This data underscores that the self-concept developed among today's teenagers is predominantly negative.

The development of an adolescent's self-concept requires substantial support from various sources, including family, peers, the environment, and mental health professionals. Family plays a crucial role in shaping an adolescent's self-concept, as they are the first individuals with whom a child interacts, laying the foundation for the child's life and providing essential evaluations of their behavior [7]. Generally, the family's primary responsibilities include nurturing and educating their children. Additionally, families serve as role models, guiding children in navigating social environments and exemplifying appropriate behaviors, attitudes, and beliefs. When adolescents receive positive parental guidance throughout their growth and development, it fosters the formation of a healthy self-concept.

Childcare within the family should involve collaboration between fathers and mothers. Father involvement is defined as the active participation of fathers in their roles related to education, emotional well-being, and daily activities of children [3]. The manner in which fathers educate and interact with their children significantly influences the development and formation of self-concept [8]. The phenomenon of a "fatherless country" in Indonesia raises major concerns in studies on childcare. Patriarchal culture and work-related busyness often result in minimal involvement of fathers in caregiving. This lack of engagement has the potential to impact various aspects of child development, including cognitive stimulation, executive function, and the formation of sexual identity.

Several studies have demonstrated that a father's parenting plays a significant role in shaping an adolescent's self-concept, with both positive and negative effects [4]. Research indicates that children who experience warm, sensitive, and responsive parenting from their fathers tend to enjoy better psychological well-being, higher academic performance, improved social competence, and more advanced moral development and prosocial behavior [9]. Furthermore, children who maintain a close emotional bond with their fathers are more likely to exhibit controlled or positive attitudes in their surroundings. The findings suggest that a child's positive perception of their father's involvement correlates with a reduced likelihood of engaging in premarital sex [8]. Additionally, effective fathering can enhance a child's sense of empathy. Conversely, children who spend less time with their fathers may display negative behaviors in an attempt to seek attention. Adolescent girls who lack father figures

are at a higher risk of experiencing unplanned pregnancies, low self-esteem, school and college dropouts, poverty, divorce, and promiscuity [10].

The results of the researcher's interview with the homeroom teacher of VII class at SMPN 4 Pariaman revealed that students with low levels of self-confidence were often those whose fathers were preoccupied with work in the fields, selling at the market, or living away from home. In contrast, disruptive students tended to come from households where fathers frequently expressed anger and showed little concern for their children's academic development. Among the 20 students interviewed, 10 reported feeling afraid in class, 5 admitted to teasing their classmates, and 5 expressed a lack of motivation to attend school. Notably, 10 of these students acknowledged that whenever they engaged in misbehavior at school, their fathers never expressed anger or inquired about their actions at home. These fathers appeared indifferent to their teenage children's delinquency. This data suggests that the level of paternal involvement in these students' lives may be linked to the negative self-concept exhibited by the students.

Based on the data and findings from the literature review, it appears that a father's involvement in parenting is related to the development of a child's self-concept. Consequently, the researcher conducted a study to explore the relationship between paternal involvement in parenting and the self-concept of female adolescents at SMPN 4 Kota Pariaman. The formulation of the problem in this study is how the relationship between father's parenting involvement and the formation of adolescent self-concept at SMPN 4 Pariaman. The purpose of this study was to determine the correlation between a father's parenting involvement and the self-concept of female adolescents at SMPN 4 Kota Pariaman, West Sumatra Province.

2. METHODOLOGY

This study employs a quantitative research design with a cross-sectional approach. The independent variable is the father's involvement in parenting, while the dependent variable is the adolescent self-concept. The research was conducted on July 11, 2024. The population of this study was 122 students of class VII of SMPN 4 Pariaman. The sample of this study was 53 students of class VII of SMPN 4 Pariaman. Grade VII was selected as the research sample because the respondents, aged 11 to 12 years, are in a transitional phase of adolescence characterized by stabilizing physical, psychological, and social development. During this period, they begin to search for their identity, which enhances their ability to think abstractly, evaluate situations, draw conclusions, and solve complex problems. At this stage, adolescents can recognize and assess the environmental influences on their self-concept, particularly the impact of their father's involvement in parenting. The sampling method used was random sampling with the inclusion criteria of class VII students of SMPN 4 Kota Pariaman, present at school, willing to be respondents, and able to read and write.

The research utilized a questionnaire as the primary instrument. Self-concept was assessed using a Likert scale comprising 15 questions. The results of the self-concept assessment are considered positive if the score exceeds 50% and negative if the score falls below 50%. The father's parenting involvement was evaluated through a questionnaire consisting of 15 questions based on a Likert scale. A score above 50% indicates high levels of parenting involvement, while a score below 50% reflects low levels of involvement. The questionnaires underwent validity and reliability testing. This study utilized both primary and secondary data. Primary data were collected directly from students' responses to the questionnaire, while secondary data were obtained from a summary provided by the homeroom teacher of Class VII at SMPN 4 Pariaman. Data analysis was performed using univariate and bivariate methods. Univariate analysis was conducted to determine the frequency distribution and percentage of variables related to fathers' parenting involvement and adolescents' self-concept. Bivariate tests were employed to examine the relationship between fathers' parenting involvement and adolescents' self-concept at SMPN 4 Pariaman. In this study, the bivariate analysis utilized the Chi-Square statistical test with a significance level of 5%. The results of both univariate and bivariate analyses are presented in the attached table. The analysis was conducted using SPSS software, version 29.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1.1 Result Research

1.1.1 Univariate analysis

Univariate analysis was conducted on the variables of paternal involvement in parenting and adolescent self-concept at SMPN 4 Pariaman. The results of the univariate analysis are presented in Table 1 below.

Table 1. Frequency distribution and percentage of fathers' parenting involvement

Father's involvement	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
Good	24	45.3
Less	29	54.7
Total	53	100

The data presented in Table 1 indicates that the level of father involvement in the care of their adolescent children at SMPN 4 Pariaman is categorized as low, with 29 participants (54.7%) falling into this category. This suggests that 54.7% of respondents with high scores to the questionnaire, scoring above 50%. Additionally, the results of the univariate analysis regarding the formation of self-concept in adolescents at SMPN 4 Pariaman can be seen in Table 2.

Table 2. Frequency distribution and percentage of self-concept in adolescents

Self-concept	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
Positive	21	39.62
Negative	32	60.38
Total	53	100

Based on Table 2, it is evident that the majority of teenagers possess a negative self-concept, with 32 participants (60.38%) reflecting this sentiment. This indicates that teenagers at SMPN 4 Pariaman frequently perceive aspects of themselves in a negative light.

1.1.2 Bivariate Analysis

The bivariate analysis of the relationship between fathers' parenting involvement and the development of adolescent self-concept at SMPN 4 Pariaman is presented in Table 3.

Table 3. Frequency distribution, percentage, and relationship between fathers' parenting involvement and self-concept in adolescents at SMPN 4 Pariaman

Father's involvement	Self-concept				Total	P-value	OR	
	Positive		Negative					
	F	%	f	%	f	%		
Good	20	90.9	4	12.9	24	45.3	0.002	8.5
Less	2	9.1	27	87.10	29	54.7		
Total	22	100	31	100	53	100		

The data presented in Table 3 indicates that adolescents with strong father's involvement in parenting are more likely to develop a positive self-concept, with 20 participants (90.9%) out of a total of 24 (45.3%) exhibiting this trait. In contrast, adolescents with limited paternal involvement predominantly form a negative self-concept, with 27 participants (87.10%) out of 29 (54.7%) falling into

this category. The results of the statistical analysis reveal a p-value of 0.002, which is less than the 5% significance level ($p < 0.05$). This finding suggests father's involvement in parenting and the development of self-concept among adolescents at SMPN 4 Pariaman. Furthermore, the odds ratio (OR) of 8.50 indicates that adolescents with actively involved fathers are 8.50 times more likely to cultivate a positive self-concept. Conversely, those with less involved fathers are also 8.50 times more likely to develop a negative self-concept.

1.2 Discussion

1.1.1 Univariate analysis

Based on the analysis of the study conducted by the researcher, it is evident that the majority of students, specifically 29 participants (54.7%), have fathers who are minimally involved in their upbringing. In contrast, 24 participants (45.3%) report having fathers who are actively engaged in their development. This indicates that more than half of the students at SMPN 4 Pariaman experience limited father's involvement in their upbringing. Related studies further corroborate this finding, revealing that a significant number of adolescents, specifically 78 out of 100 students (78.0%), report having fathers who are less involved in their upbringing [8]. Additionally, another study indicates that less than half (47.5%) of students do not receive paternal involvement in their family upbringing [11].

According to Erikson's developmental theory, adolescents are individuals aged 12 to 18 years. One of the key developmental tasks during this stage is the search for self-identity. At this age, adolescents often experience confusion regarding their identity and societal roles. Consequently, they may struggle to explore their identities and roles within society. A failure to engage in this exploration can lead to feelings of isolation or separation from their peers. Therefore, social interactions and challenges within their environment are crucial for fostering healthy social development [12].

According to Bronfenbrenner's ecological systems theory, the environment significantly influences the social development of children, particularly adolescents. The family environment serves as a microsystem that interacts with and directly impacts children's development. Consequently, parental involvement in parenting can affect the success of adolescents in achieving developmental tasks, such as identity formation [13]. One crucial element within this microsystem is the father. A father's involvement in parenting plays a vital role in shaping an adolescent's self-identity, ultimately contributing to the development of a positive or negative self-concept.

Father's involvement in parenting encompasses the participation, contribution, and execution of a father's role in the growth and development of his child across various domains, including physical, social, cognitive, emotional, and spiritual aspects. This involvement is characterized by the father's active engagement in daily activities with the child, which includes direct interaction, providing warmth, monitoring and guiding the child's activities, and fulfilling the child's needs and requirements. A father's role in parenting also entails planning, being attentive, monitoring progress, evaluating situations, expressing concern, and praying for the child's growth and development. A father's affectionate and warm parenting style positively influences the child's cognitive development and fosters positive feelings and intentions. The father's supportive and nurturing demeanor is closely linked to the formation of the child's character, encompassing emotional, intellectual, physical, and social dimensions [6].

Father involvement can foster a sense of affection, attention, empathy, strong social relationships, and moral maturity, as evidenced by the expression of prosocial and positive behaviors [7]. The researcher assumes that a father's involvement is crucial in raising his child. Children who receive less care from their fathers often exhibit more negative behaviors, while those who receive attentive care typically demonstrate a more positive outlook on life. Therefore, it is essential to emphasize to fathers the significance of their contributions in nurturing and developing their children, particularly as they enter their teenage years.

Father involvement in parenting significantly influences the development of self-concept in children entering adolescence. The results presented in Table 2 indicate that the majority of self-concepts

among students at SMPN 4 Pariaman are negative, with 32 participants (60.38%) exhibiting negative self-concepts, while only a small portion, 21 participants (39.62%), demonstrate positive self-concepts. Additionally, the findings reveal that adolescents can develop both positive and negative self-concepts. In a study of Batak adolescents, the average self-concept was found to be positive (70.24%) [8]. Similarly, research conducted at SMK Bani Saleh showed that adolescents exhibited predominantly positive self-concepts (93%) compared to negative self-concepts (7%) [9].

Self-concept refers to the mental image of one's appearance and personality that is ingrained within an individual. In adolescents, self-concept encompasses the attitudes they hold while evaluating themselves and their surroundings, which in turn fosters their confidence to engage in various activities throughout their lives. The development of a positive or negative self-concept can be influenced by both intrinsic and extrinsic factors. Intrinsic factors include physical and intellectual conditions, while extrinsic factors encompass influences from family, friends, and the broader environment. Family, especially the involvement of father's care, greatly determines the formation of a child's self-concept.

According to the researcher's assume, an adolescent's self-concept is developed during the teenage years. The curiosity that adolescents have about themselves and their surroundings influences whether their self-concept is positive or negative. A positive self-concept is reflected in attitudes such as confidence in their abilities, acceptance of their shortcomings without feelings of inferiority, openness to criticism and suggestions, optimism about the future, and the ability to interact well with others. Conversely, a negative self-concept is characterized by a lack of confidence, frequent self-doubt, a focus on shortcomings and failures, feelings of unworthiness regarding appreciation or love, a tendency to give up easily and fear of trying new things, as well as difficulty accepting praise and a tendency to reject help.

1.1.2 Bivariate analysis

The statistical analysis revealed a p-value of 0.002, which is below the 5% significance level ($p < 0.05$). This indicates a significant relationship between fathers' involvement in parenting and the development of self-concept among adolescents at SMPN 4 Pariaman. Additional research also demonstrates a significant correlation between fathers' involvement in parenting and adolescent self-concept [3][8][15][18][19][21][22]. Furthermore, fathers' involvement in parenting positively influences the development of adolescent self-confidence [22][23]. Research findings indicate that adolescents who grow up without paternal care due to divorce express more negative self-concepts, such as feelings of being lost and difficulties in adjusting to their environment. In contrast, adolescents who do not receive paternal care due to death tend to have more positive self-concepts, which are reflected in their acceptance of the situation, optimism, and strong cognitive skills [25].

The development and formation of self-concept in adolescents significantly depend on the support of their surrounding environment, particularly the care provided by parents, including both fathers and mothers. The involvement of fathers in parenting plays a crucial role in a child's future development. Active fathers who engage in raising their children can foster a positive self-concept, while those who are less involved may contribute to the development of a negative self-concept. Therefore, it is essential for fathers to demonstrate their involvement in their children's upbringing to cultivate a positive self-concept, especially during the critical adolescent years. Effective parenting strategies that fathers can adopt include demonstrating loving care, providing unwavering support with thoughtful consideration, engaging in positive and warm interactions, taking responsibility, spending quality time with their children, and meeting their children's financial needs [25].

The odds ratio (OR) of 8.50 indicates that adolescents with actively involved fathers are 8.50 times more likely to develop a positive self-concept. Conversely, those with less involved fathers are also 8.50 times more likely to cultivate a negative self-concept. Paternal involvement in parenting is correlated with 47.6% of the formation of self-concept in SMK Negeri 4 Kendari [3]. Meanwhile, other studies indicate that paternal involvement accounts for 67.1% of self-concept development in SMK Bani Saleh [18]. The findings from this study, along with other research on paternal involvement and self-concept

formation, demonstrate a positive correlation. It can be concluded that strong paternal involvement in parenting fosters a positive self-concept, whereas minimal paternal involvement may contribute to the development of a negative self-concept.

The researcher assumes that a father's involvement in raising children is crucial for fostering a positive self-concept, particularly during adolescence. Insufficient paternal care, or a complete lack of it, can contribute to rising mental health issues and delinquency among adolescents. Therefore, it is essential for fathers to be actively engaged in their children's upbringing.

4. CONCLUSIONS

Based on the research findings, it can be concluded that there is a significant relationship between fathers' parenting involvement and the development of adolescent self-concept at SMPN 4 Pariaman, West Sumatra Province. The suggestion in this study is that fathers can become more involved and play an active role in raising their children, particularly adolescents, to prevent the formation of negative self-concepts that can ultimately lead to societal issues. This finding can be the basis for the need to provide intervention in the form of counseling related to family involvement, especially fathers, in adolescents who are still in school. Suggestions for further research include the necessity of conducting longitudinal studies on father involvement, focusing on both the quantity and quality of involvement, and their impact on educational achievement, delinquent behavior, and adolescent psychological well-being.

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